

Jul and Aug plantings, but increased for Sep plantings and reached 12 insects/sweep for Oct plantings. The population declined during the relatively cool months of Dec and Jan (Fig. 1).

Incidence of the bacilliform virus (RTBV) and the spherical virus (RTSV) increased with leafhopper populations. Regardless of month of planting, RTSV incidence was present (Fig. 1b). Infection with RTSV alone did not cause RTV symptoms. Dual infection with RTBV and RTSV was observed in Jun, Sep, and Oct plantings. Regardless of month of planting, TN1 was most infected, followed by IR36 and IR42 (Fig. 1c). IR50, IR58, and IR64 were seldom infected. □

Average density of the vector leafhoppers (a) and incidence of RTBV and RTSV (b) at 30 d after transplanting in 6 varieties transplanted monthly from Jun 1985 to Jan 1986; and incidence in each variety regardless of month of transplanting (c).

A scoring system for rice yellow mottle virus disease (RYMV)

V. T. John and G. Thottapilly, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Nigeria

RYMV, an African specific disease of lowland rice varieties, has been studied for its etiology and to screen for resistance. But a standard evaluation system for this disease has not been reported.

The disease is systemic and variable under different growing conditions. Symptoms vary with age of host. Different varieties show different symptoms. Even after repeated inoculations, some immune varieties do not show any virus serologically, even

by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Others with little or no symptoms give positive reactions with ELISA.

The scoring system we propose is compatible with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Scores are based on leaf color, mottling, plant height, flowering,

Table 2. Differential varieties for RYMV.

Score	Resistance grade	Varieties
0	HR	<i>Oryza glaberrima</i> accessions such as Tog 5612, Tog 5681
2	R	Moroberekan, LAC23
4	MR	OS6, ITA235
7	S	BG90-2, IR5
9	HS	ITA212

Table 1. Scoring system for RYMV.

Score	Resistance ^a	Leaf color	Stunting	Flowering	Sero-diagnosis ^b	
					ELISA	Agar-gel diffusion
0	HR	Green	Nil	Normal	-	-
1	R	Green	Nil	Normal	+	±
2	R	Green	Nil	Normal	++	+(weak)
3	R	Green with sparse dots/streaks	Negligible	Normal	+++	+
4	MR	Green with visible mottling	Slight	Normal	+++	++
5	MR	Light green, mottled	25%	Slight delay	Highly positive	
6	S	Pale green	50%	Delayed	Highly positive	
7	S	Pale yellow	75%	Delayed	Highly positive	
8	S	Yellow	>75%	No flowering	Highly positive	
9	HS	Yellow, orange	>75%	Death of plants	Highly positive	

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, and HS = highly susceptible. ^b± = doubtful, - = negative, + = low virus content, ++ = high virus content, +++ = very high virus content.

and sero-reaction determined by agar-gel diffusion and ELISA techniques. The serological techniques are for restricted use in critical laboratory tests. Most field scores can be based on visual symptoms.

In the score range, 0 represents immunity and 9 extreme susceptibility (death of infected plant) (Table 1).

The actual score range is typified by certain rice varieties which when inoculated display characteristic symptoms (Table 2). □

Crown sheath rot incidence in West Bengal

D. K. Nayak and H.S. Chakrabarti, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

Early symptoms of crown sheath rot were reddish brown lesions in patches on the outer leaf sheaths at the crown of the plants. Gradually, the lesions spread throughout the crown sheaths and became dark brown to black. At maturity, clusters of perithecia were produced in the lesions. In severely affected clumps, the culms rotted causing incomplete exertion and leaf drying (see figure).

Microscopic examination of the rotted crown sheaths showed the

Incidence of crown sheath rot disease in rice in West Bengal.

presence of *Gaeumannomyces graminis* var. *graminis*, characterized by hyphae with distinct hyphopodia and beaked perithecia that produced unitunicate asci with eight long, curved ascospores. □

Nitrogen level, cultivar, and *R. solani* isolate effect on sheath blight (ShB) development

A. K.M. Shahjahan, N. Fabellar, and T. W. Mew, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

Eight rice varieties differing in duration, plant height, and ShB susceptibility were grown in 30-cm-diam pots in the greenhouse with 2 N levels: 1.6 g and 3.2 g/pot. N was applied in 2 equal splits at 21 d after transplanting and at panicle initiation. Staggered planting synchronized booting.

Ten isolates of *R. solani* differing in growth rate, sclerotia production, and culture type were selected from 98 isolates collected from rice, grass, millet, maize, water hyacinth, and weeds. Plants were inoculated at booting with inocula prepared in a rice hull:rice grain medium. About 100 ml of the inocula was placed between tillers. Inoculated plants were covered with polyethylene sheets at night.

Lesion height/plant height was recorded at 5d intervals. The ratios of

leaf to sheath area infection were compared 28 d after inoculation.

Development of relative lesion height (RLH) and percent area infected (PAI) by isolates of *R. solani* differed among varieties. The influence of N level was apparent only at later stages of lesion

development. However, there was an isolate × N interaction.

Isolate RS72-1 produced the lowest RLH as well as PAI in all varieties and was the least virulent isolate tested (Fig. 1,2). The other isolates developed higher RLH and PAI in IR58 and

1. Vertical development of ShB in IR58 by different isolates of *R. solani* at 2 N levels. IRRI, 1987.